

A Preliminary Set of Numerical Experiments for the Verification and Validation of the Neutron Count Moments Implementation in PARTISN

Cade Abbott^{1,*}, Jawad Moussa², Mario Ortega², Andrew Panter³, Sandra Bogetic¹

¹University of Tennessee, Knoxville, TN; ²Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM;

³University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803815

ABSTRACT

Neutron noise analysis techniques, such as Feynman-Y analysis, are commonly used to characterize samples of special nuclear material (SNM). These techniques depend on moments of the neutron count distribution to infer sample characteristics such as the prompt neutron decay constant, α . This work seeks to verify and validate the stochastic neutronics implementation for moments of the neutron count distribution in the Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) neutral particle transport code PARAllel TIme-dependent SN (PARTISN). For applications where computing α is of interest, a series of numerical experiments are performed in PARTISN and compared against analog Monte Carlo simulations using the Monte Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) code. Three numerical experiments were performed to verify and validate (1) a user-defined neutron source and the first neutron count moment, (2) moments of multiplying systems consisting of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu spheres, and (3) neutron kinetic parameters and Feynman-Y as a function of increasing time-gate. Results show good agreement between PARTISN and MCNP thus demonstrating the efficacy of using PARTISN and the neutron count moments implementation as a modeling technique for neutron noise analysis.

Keywords: Feynman-Y, MCNP, Neutron Count Moments, PARTISN, Verification & Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron noise analysis techniques are of high importance to various applications including nuclear safeguards and reactor operations [1, 2]. These techniques are commonly used for the characterization of Special Nuclear Material (SNM) and reactor diagnostics. One key parameter in such applications is the prompt neutron decay constant, α , as it provides information related to system reactivity [3]. The motivation of this work is to benchmark the neutron count moments implementation in LANL's deterministic neutral particle transport code, PARAllel TIme-dependent SN (PARTISN), for applications where calculating α is of interest [4, 5]. We suspect that this stochastic neutronics capability calculates α with a high degree of accuracy as it utilizes multiple moments of the neutron count distribution.

Three numerical experiments are performed in this work to benchmark the stochastic neutronics count moments implementation in PARTISN against analog Monte Carlo simulations. Specifically, results obtained using the count moments implementation in PARTISN are compared against simulations of the same problem using the Monte Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) code [6]. The experiments were designed in a hierarchical fashion with increasing complexity. All models assumed an ideal $4-\pi$ detector, thus no distinction is made between moments of the neutron leakage distribution and neutron count moments. Nonetheless, the first numerical experiment verifies the first moment of the neutron count distribution (i.e., the mean number of counts) for a user-defined source in a void. This experiment is used as a starting point for its simplicity as the leakage distribution is expected to match the source rate and can be easily verified. The second experiment validates the first moment of the count distribution and neutron multiplication values for a ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu sphere and compares results between MCNP and PARTISN.

*Corresponding author email: cabbott9@vols.utk.edu

Lastly, the third experiment compares alpha values reported by MCNP and PARTISN for subcritical spheres of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu . This work contributes to verification and validation of the stochastic neutronics implementation in PARTISN thus demonstrating its efficacy as a modeling technique for neutron noise analysis.

2. NEUTRON NOISE ANALYSIS BACKGROUND

2.1. Prompt Neutron Decay Constant α and Feynman-Y

Of interest to this work is the kinetic parameter α as it allows for the estimation of a system's criticality. This parameter arises through the assumption that the neutron angular flux of a system, ψ , follows an exponential distribution with respect to time [3],

$$\psi(\vec{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}, t) = e^{\alpha t} \cdot \psi(\vec{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}). \quad (1)$$

Using this definition of α and the mean neutron generation time Λ , the criticality may be estimated [7],

$$k = \frac{1}{1 - \alpha\Lambda}. \quad (2)$$

The Feynman-Y analysis technique is used to calculate α via post-processing time series neutron detection data [8, 9]. The process begins with a time series of neutron detection events over a long detection acquisition window. By selecting a set of detection time gates, the large acquisition window may be split up into many bins for each detection time gate interval. Time-correlation information between events is extracted by computing the mean and variance of the neutron counts over each prescribed time gate. This approach is based on an important characteristic of a Poisson distribution where the mean of the distribution is equivalent to its variance. Therefore, the variance to mean ratio is expected to be unity in the absence of multiplication. Hence, the distribution's time-dependent deviation from a Poisson distribution is characteristic of a subcritical system's multiplication. The expected Feynman-Y evolution with respect to the detection time gate interval, τ , is given by

$$Y(\tau) = Y_{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1 - e^{\alpha\tau}}{\alpha\tau} \right) + 1, \quad (3)$$

where Y_{∞} is the asymptotic value of the variance-to-mean ratio [8].

2.2. Neutron Count Moments in PARTISN

The time-gated mean and variance of the neutron count distribution are needed for Feynman-Y analysis. These quantities can be readily obtained from PARTISN using the stochastic neutronics implementation of the neutron count moments [5]. The mathematical derivation of the equations appropriate to moments of the neutron count distribution are outlined in [5, 10] where the k^{th} raw moment of the neutron count distribution is given by

$$\left(-\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} - \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla}_n + \Sigma_t(\vec{r}, E) \right) \overline{n^k}(D|\vec{r}, E, \vec{\Omega}, s) = \iint dE' d\Omega' \Sigma_s(\vec{r}, E \rightarrow E'; \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\Omega}') \overline{n^k}(D|\vec{r}, E', \vec{\Omega}', s) + \bar{v} \Sigma_f(\vec{r}, E) \langle \overline{n^k} \rangle(D|\vec{r}, s) + S_k(\langle \overline{n} \rangle, \langle \overline{n^2} \rangle, \dots, \langle \overline{n^{k-1}} \rangle), q \quad (4)$$

and satisfies the final-time and boundary conditions,

$$\bar{n}^k(D|\vec{r}, E, \vec{\Omega}, t_f) = 0, \quad \vec{r} \in V; \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{n}^k(D|\vec{r}, E, \vec{\Omega}, s) = \epsilon(E)I_D(E, t), \quad \vec{r} \in \partial V, \quad \vec{n} \cdot \vec{\Omega} > 0 \quad (6)$$

for $k \geq 1$. Note that S_k in Eq. 4 is an inhomogeneous source term that depends on lower order moments of count distribution. $\epsilon(E)$ and $I_D(E, t)$ are an energy-dependent detection efficiency and an indicator function, respectively, that enable the time-gated counting with energy discrimination. Moments up to the fourth order are obtained from PARTISN using the `ith=5` input option.

3. METHODS

All numerical experiments performed in this work feature 1-D spherical models developed in both MCNP and PARTISN. Various metrics are probed using these numerical experiments in an effort to cross-validate the neutron count moments implementation in PARTISN.

A binning procedure was used to extract moments of the neutron count distribution from the time series data produced by MCNP. PARTISN does not require the same post-processing as it computes the time-gated moments directly.

As such, a Python [11] script was developed to post process the MCNP time series data. The script was made compatible with MCNP's HDF5 format of PTRAC files enabling efficient data processing. The PTRAC data consists of a single array with many time stamps corresponding to neutron leakage events. The data is trimmed to the simulation time, $t \in [0, 1 \times 10^7] sh$, to avoid the false consideration of neutrons simulated when the source is inactive. For the first detection time gate, $\tau = 0.1 sh$, for example, the entire domain is split into $0.1 sh$ intervals, resulting in a total of 1×10^8 bins. The mean and variance of the neutron counts per bin is computed and the process is repeated for multiple detector time gates such as to obtain a dataset of variance-to-mean as a function of detector time gate. Least squares regression was used to fit Eq. 3 to the data, yielding the parameters Y_∞ and α with associated uncertainties.

4. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

4.1. Void Sphere Leakage Moments

The objective of the first numerical experiment performed is to ensure that identical neutron source rates are used in subsequent MCNP and PARTISN models, indicating a proper construction of input files and detection of source particles. To do this, a void sphere is modeled in both MCNP and PARTISN with identical source rate definitions. Both models consisted of a void sphere with a radius of $r = 4.5 cm$ in which neutrons are injected with a uniform spatial and angular distribution. All space external to the sphere is also modeled as a void to ensure no neutron reflection. A neutron source rate of $\dot{Q} = 1 [n \cdot sh^{-1}]$ is specified in each model.

It can be readily shown that the expected number of detected neutrons, N , for a detector time gate, τ , of $100 sh$ is 100 neutrons. That is, both MCNP and PARTISN should yield a total of 100 leaked neutrons over $100 sh$ time-gate, given that all system parameters are defined consistently between the two models.

4.1.1. PARTISN & MCNP Models

The void sphere is discretized in PARTISN using 100 spatial points, S_{64} angular quadrature, and MENDF80 data with a 618-group energy structure from the nuclear data interface (NDI). Vacuum boundary conditions are assumed to avoid neutron reflection. A user-defined volumetric source is used in PARTISN

with units $\dot{q} [n \cdot cm^{-3} \cdot sh^{-1}]$ for each energy bin. Note that the source rate used in the PARTISN calculation must be computed to achieve a rate of 1 neutron per sh . That is achieved by dividing the desired source by the total volume of the modeled sphere to obtain a neutron rate per unit volume per unit time. Given that the radius of the sphere is $4.5 cm$, this yields a source rate of $0.00262 [n \cdot cm^{-3} \cdot sh^{-1}]$. It also noted that all neutrons are uniformly born in the $E \in [15, 17] MeV$ range and the problem was simulated over $200 sh$ with the detector being switched on after the first $100 sh$ to allow for spatiotemporal convergence of the neutron flux. Using the `ith=5` feature, neutron count moments are calculated and written to an output file.

In MCNP, the void sphere is constructed using the `S0` macrobody. The region external to the sphere is set to have neutron importance of zero. The `SDEF` card is used to specify that neutrons are uniformly emitted in space, angle, and time with an energy distribution equivalent to the PARTISN model: $E \in [15, 17] MeV$. The problem is simulated over $1 \times 10^7 sh$ with `NPS` also set to 1×10^7 to match a source rate of $\dot{Q} = 1 [n \cdot sh^{-1}]$. The Python script described above is used to bin the data in $100 sh$ intervals and the mean is computed to obtain an averaged detection count. Using the `PTRAC` feature in MCNP, surface crossing events are written to an output file, containing information of all neutrons that leaked from the system.

4.1.2. Results and Discussion

The output files from both codes are analyzed to determine the number of neutrons that leaked during the $\tau = 100 sh$ detection phase. As expected, both MCNP and PARTISN reported 100 detected neutrons with negligible uncertainty, confirming the source rate of $\dot{Q} = 1 [n \cdot sh^{-1}]$. The results of the first numerical experiment illustrate that identical sources were used in both MCNP and PARTISN.

4.2. Multiplying System Leakage Moments

The second numerical experiment performed is aimed at obtaining a consistent result between PARTISN and MCNP for the count moments from two different spheres consisting of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu , respectively. For simplicity, spontaneous fission and delayed neutron production are neglected and neutron cross-section data are pulled from the ENDF-VIII nuclear data library at room temperature. The density of the ^{235}U is assumed to be $19.1 [g \cdot cm^{-3}]$ while the density of the ^{239}Pu is assumed to be $19.8 [g \cdot cm^{-3}]$. In addition to counting the number of neutrons detected, the criticality, k_{eff} , of each system was calculated by MCNP and PARTISN.

4.2.1. PARTISN & MCNP Models

The PARTISN models featured the same discretization in space, energy, and angle as the previous experiment. The system is simulated over $200 sh$, with the detector being switched on after $100 sh$. The same source rate and source spectrum are also used. The only difference from the previous experiment is that the models included independent homogeneous spheres of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu .

The MCNP models are similar to the previous experiment except the void sphere is replaced with a sphere of ^{235}U and a sphere of ^{239}Pu , producing two cases. Additionally, the `FMULT SHIFT=1` card is used to ensure that MCNP samples the induced fission neutron multiplicity probability distribution function (PDF). This is an important specification as the variance would be impacted significantly if the multiplicity data was altered. Lastly, a `CUT:N 2j 0 0` card is utilized to run MCNP in analog mode. Again, this is important for variance preservation.

4.2.2. Results & Discussion

Table I shows the mean number of neutron counts compared across MCNP and PARTISN for the described models in addition to the k_{eff} of each system.

Table I. Fissile Sphere Criticality and First Leakage Moment

Composition	PARTISN k	MCNP k	PARTISN Mean	MCNP Mean
^{235}U	0.5706	0.5726 ± 0.0004	311.6	311.7 ± 0.004
^{239}Pu	0.9203	0.9229 ± 0.0005	1476.8	1478.3 ± 0.2

The results presented in Table I demonstrate good agreement between MCNP and PARTISN for the criticality and first leakage moment. This confirms that similar nuclear data is being used for both materials and that modeling assumptions present small discrepancies. Additionally, this demonstrates that MCNP and PARTISN produce similar values of neutron multiplication for both ^{239}Pu and ^{235}U . Though exact alignment is not observed, the discrepancies are small enough such that disagreement is likely be attributed to some of the unique simplifications required by the PARTISN model. For example, spatial and angular discretizations carry a truncation error as a result of the approximation of a continuous derivative. Furthermore, the cross-section collapse from continuous energy to a multi-group energy structure causes differences in nuclear data accessed by each code.

4.3. Time-Dependent Feynman-Y Comparison

The final numerical experiment compares higher-order moments between PARTISN and MCNP. Specifically, the detector time gate is varied to analyze the time-correlated kinetic parameter α through Feynman-Y analysis. The same ^{239}Pu and ^{235}U spheres from the previous experiment are used for this analysis in MCNP and PARTISN.

4.3.1. PARTISN & MCNP Models

In PARTISN, the fissile spheres are modeled in the same way as the previous numerical experiment, however the detector acquisition period is varied to analyze the time-dependent variance of the first two moments. In total, 50 separate input scripts were prepared for various detector time gates in $\tau \in [0.1, 100]$ sh for both systems, spaced logarithmically. Using the count moment feature in PARTISN, the neutron count moments are calculated for each time gate. Lastly, a Python script is used to fit the Feynman-Y equation given by Eq. 3 to the data via least squares regression. From this, the asymptotic and exponential behavior of these systems are quantified.

In MCNP, the fissile spheres are modeled the same as previous numerical experiments with the exception of multiple time gates being used to analyze system kinetics. Using the same PTRAC feature as before, all neutrons that leaked from the system are recorded in an output file with a time stamp for each leakage. The data is then truncated such that all time stamps were within $t \in [0, 1 \times 10^7]$ sh. This time domain is binned for each of the 50 detector time gates used in the PARTISN calculation. The mean and variance of the neutron counts in the bins are computed and a Python script is then used to fit the Feynman-Y equation to the variance-to-mean profile via least squares regression.

4.3.2. Results & Discussion

A total of 50 detector time gates were used for the ^{235}U and the ^{239}Pu system. The moments are collected from PARTISN by parsing each output file while the aforementioned Python script is used to extract the moments from MCNP. Figures 1a and 1b compare the first moment as a function of increasing time-gate

Figure 1. Numerical results comparing first moment, second moment, and Feynman-Y as calculated by MCNP and PARTISN for subcritical spheres of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu .

from PARTISN and MCNP for the ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu systems, respectively. Similarly, Figures 1c and 1d compare the second moment computed from each code. Lastly, Figures 1e and 1f show the evolution of the variance-to-mean ratio with the Feynman-Y fit for both systems. Results of the numerical fits are illustrated in Table II.

Table II. Feynman-Y Fitted Parameters

Composition	Numerical Code	γ_{∞} [n]	α [sh^{-1}]
^{235}U	PARTISN	8.57 ± 0.23	-1.80 ± 0.22
^{235}U	MCNP	8.91 ± 0.22	-1.78 ± 0.21
^{239}Pu	PARTISN	297.5 ± 0.3	-0.408 ± 0.002
^{239}Pu	MCNP	306.9 ± 0.3	-0.399 ± 0.002

These results illustrate the alignment between the mean and variance across a broad domain of time gates for both ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu in addition to α and the asymptotic value of the Feynman-Y. PARTISN is observed to consistently underestimate the MCNP values, but this is consistent with the trends in the criticality estimates in Table I. Similar to the second numerical experiment, minor discrepancies are observed. The sources of these discrepancies is likely due to the discretizations used in the PARTISN

models.

5. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, good alignment between MCNP and PARTISN is observed for each of the three numerical experiments outlined in this work providing good benchmarking neutron count moments implementation in PARTISN. The discrepancies between the two codes is likely attributed to the differences in nuclear data. Primarily, it is suspected that the shift from continuous energy in MCNP to a multi-group energy structure in PARTISN constitute the majority of the observed discrepancies. Nonetheless, these results highlight the capabilities of PARTISN as a robust tool for modeling neutron kinetics via the neutron count moments implementation.

The next step will include modeling a nuclear benchmark experiment in PARTISN for comparison with experimental values. Work is currently underway to model the SCRaP benchmark featured in the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP). Additionally, future work will evaluate the accuracy of various approaches to compute α within PARTISN. It is suspected that the stochastic neutronics count moments implementation produces a more accurate value compared to that of the deterministic eigenvalue solver for subcritical systems as it incorporates higher order neutron count moments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the U.S. Department of Energy through the Los Alamos National Laboratory. Los Alamos National Laboratory is operated by Triad National Security, LLC, for the National Nuclear Security Administration of U.S. Department of Energy (Contract No. 89233218CNA000001).

This material is based upon work supported by the Department of Energy National Nuclear Security Administration through Defense Nuclear Nonproliferation's Enabling Capabilities in Technology Consortium under Award Number DE-NA0004197.

This material is based upon work supported under a Department of Energy, Office of Nuclear Energy University Nuclear Leadership Program Graduate Fellowship.

This work was cleared for unlimited release by Los Alamos National Laboratory: LA-UR-25-30516

REFERENCES

- [1] W. H. Geist, P. A. Santi, M. T. Swinhoe, et al. *Nondestructive Assay of Nuclear Materials for Safeguards and Security*. Springer Cham (2025).
- [2] D. Langner, J. Stewart, M. Pickrell, M. Krick, N. Ensslin, and W. Harker. "Application guide to neutron multiplicity counting." Technical Report LA-13422-M, Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM (1998).
- [3] E. E. Lewis and W. F. Miller. *Computational methods of neutron transport*. John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, NY (1984). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/5538794>.
- [4] R. E. Alcouffe, R. S. Baker, J. A. Dahl, E. D. Fichtl, S. A. Turner, R. C. Ward, and R. J. Zerr. "PARTISN: A Time-Dependent, Parallel, Neutral Particle Transport Code System." Technical Report LA-UR-08-7258, Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM (2008).
- [5] J. R. Moussa, A. K. Prinja, N. Hart, and E. Davis. "Deterministic computation of leakage neutron multiplicity moments in PARTISN." In *Proceedings of International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science & Engineering*. American Nuclear Society, Niagara Falls, Canada (2023).

- [6] J. A. Kulesza, T. R. Adams, J. C. Armstrong, S. R. Bolding, F. B. Brown, J. S. Bull, T. P. Burke, A. R. Clark, R. A. Forster, III, J. F. Giron, T. S. Grieve, C. J. Josey, R. L. Martz, G. W. McKinney, E. J. Pearson, M. E. Rising, C. J. Solomon, Jr., S. Swaminarayan, T. J. Trahan, S. C. Wilson, and A. J. Zukaitis. "MCNP[®] Code Version 6.3.0 Theory & User Manual." Technical Report LA-UR-22-30006, Rev. 1, Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM (2022).
- [7] W. M. Stacey. *Nuclear reactor physics*. John Wiley & Sons (2018).
- [8] R. P. Feynman. "Statistical behavior of neutron chains." Technical Report LA-591-Del, Los Alamos National Laboratory (1946).
- [9] R. Feynman, F. De Hoffmann, and R. Serber. "Dispersion of the neutron emission in U-235 fission." *Journal of Nuclear Energy (1954)*, **volume 3**(1), pp. 64–IN10 (1956). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0891391956900420>.
- [10] J. R. Moussa. *Methods for Efficient Computation of Neutron Multiplicity Distributions and SNM Sample Characterization*. Ph.D. thesis, University of New Mexico (2024).
- [11] "Python: A Programming Language." <https://www.python.org/>.